
**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE, INNOVATION AND
EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES (ONLINE) - ISSN: 2717-7130**

Vol 1 Issue: 4 pp: 762-767

JEL Codes: L8, Z2

CHEN K. (2020). "Exploration of the Orienteering Theoretical APP Module Design",
Vol: 1 Issue: 4 pp: 762-767

Key Words: Orienteering; recreational Orienteering; Orienteering theoretical App modules

Article Type Review Article

Exploration of the Orienteering Theoretical APP Module Design

Arrived Date	Accepted Date	Published Date
27.08.2020	03.09.2020	31.10.2020

Ke Chen

ABSTRACT

With an acceleration in the combination of Information Technology and subject pedagogy, mobile Internet education has made a further progress and interactive Live-broadcasting education has occupied a pivotal position so that Orienteering theoretical study is pressed for any educational technology support. This study principally investigates the teaching content and strategies of Orienteering theoretical study, proposes design ideas and analyses the design framework of Orienteering theoretical APP modules, ending up with the prospect of Orienteering theoretical APP modules.

Research background

According to the competitive and recreational characteristics of Orienteering, it can be categorized as competitive Orienteering and recreational counterpart, with each carrying different focus and teaching demands. At present, the type of Orienteering that is widely adapted to schools education is the one that has the merits like improving participants' intelligence and physical strength, encouraging them to take adventures with excitement, and developing their coping strategies and decision-making ability. Meanwhile, experiential teaching helps enhance learners' aspiration and physical health and serves as mental adjustment. Moreover, it also trains students' quality such as strong sportsmanship and determination. According to the benefits of Orienteering, teaching syllabus of Orienteering should make the recreational Orienteering as the basic teaching objective so as to achieve the goal of arising students interests of this sport by enhancing the enjoyment of it and form in a habit of working out with Orienteering constantly. The domestic developers has applied Internet technology used in campus Orienteering APP, in which they attempted to combine Orienteering and running route. An Orienteering APP named Sunshine Sports was used in Hangzhou University of Technology where the developers set up some fixed sign-in points for students in certain period and with certain sign-in numbers. With the record of those points, every runner's route could be random and the computer would analyze their running route and send each student their personal final analysis report in their mobile phones. Another innovative practice happened in Jiangsu Nanjing Changjiang Road Primary School where physical education teachers took advantage of the connection between digital devices like projector, smart phone and tablet computer in their physical education work.

Moreover, reported by *Yangzi River Daily*, Wuhan College implemented an Running APP which was in correlation to freshmen's physical examination quality in 2017. When using this APP, users were able to choose whichever running routes they like and the system would accumulate their mileage: 52 kilometers was the pass criteria for males if they didn't want to lose the credits. Above all, using running as a sign-in mode was similar to the practice of Orienteering, which was a representative example for

The Sports Department of Guangdong University of Foreign Studies, Guangzhou Guangdong 510420
0000-0002-7214-0235

Volume: 1, Issue: 4, October 2020
issjournal.com

applying Internet Technology in Orienteering. This kind of interaction received substantial positive feedback from students and significantly reduced teachers' workload. It is a brand new notion to correlate Internet Technology and pedagogy. The application of Internet Technology assists the improvement of teaching quality, provides students with the novel experience and shows the decent teaching essence of Orienteering. There are several domestic Orienteering APP, such as Running Orienteering, Mini-field Orienteering and so on. All of them are equipped with the professional GPS assistance programme and mobile phone location function, providing Orienteering maps, satellite sign-in mode and recording relevant information when the users are running and forming the movement locus as reference. Apart from Orienteering, the other APP are exercise and fitness APP that endeavor to popularize the Orienteering in China. However, currently there is limited theory development about Orienteering APP which puts the theoretical study of Orienteering into passive position and there is no relative module development for Orienteering theoretical study.

The analysis of Orienteering theoretical study module

The orientation of Orienteering learning objectives

The orientation of Orienteering learning objectives should be adapted to the curriculum setting of the curriculum teaching syllabus which requires that the objectives should follow the progressive principles so that they can enable students to understand the basic knowledge, skills, and ability theories of Orienteering so that they can know about the basic condition, competition rules and the principle of judge which they should put into practice in the real life Orienteering.

The analysis of Orienteering learning content

In the real teaching circumstances, there is no clear line between theory and practice. Learners are supposed to apply the theories they learn to practice so that they can internalize the Orienteering knowledge. Orienteering pays much attention in practical use, which means that everyone should organize the professional knowledge in their own ways and enhance the flexibility of knowledge-use so as to make a great progress. Competitive Orienteering and its recreational counterpart emphasize on different aspects of theoretical study, such as specific technical theory, competition technical theory, maps comprehension and cartographic drawing, physical training theory principle and judgement are beneficial for learning competitive Orienteering; practical maps knowledge, map illustration recognition, the usage of compass and location, reference choosing and eyesight simplification, field survival training and competition appreciation are for recreational one. (see figure 1)

Additionally, the time required for theoretical study is demanding but there is insufficient time arrangement in schools for Orienteering theoretical learning. Therefore, we should suggest learners to use their spare time for theoretical study and find interest-arising tools or methods to boost their motivation.

Number	Teaching content	Pedagogy	Estimated duration(hour)
1	Introduction to Orienteering; Orientation and development of Orienteering; Physical exercise value of Orienteering	Explanation	2
2	Fundamental practical knowledge of map; Map color; Symbol; Contour line	Explanation; Pictures	2
3	Map symbol recognition; Map scale ; Symbol of objects; Instruction for sign-in points	Explanation; Pictures; Video clips	4
4	Instruction of compass; General orientation; Specific orientation	Pictures; Video clip; practical demonstration	2
5	Professional technical knowledge;	Explanation;	4

	Reference-decision; Eyesight simplification; Field running; Route-decision	Pictures; Video clip; Practice	
6	Professional competition technical knowledge; 100-meter run strategy; Point race strategy; Map corporation skills for team race	Explanation; Pictures; Video clip; Practice	6
7	Maps comprehension and cartographic drawing; Base map drawing; Route map drawing etc.	Practice	12
8	Physical training theory	Explanation; Practice	4
9	Competition principles and judgement	Explanation; Pictures; Video clips	2
10	Field survival training; Outdoor extending knowledge	Explanation; Pictures; Video clips; Practice	4
11	Race appreciation	Pictures; Video clips; Live-broadcasting	2
12	Race introduction; Chinese Orienteering race; International Orienteering race; Competitive principles of each kind of race	Pictures and text; Video clips	2
13	Introduction of sports-ware and equipment;	Pictures and text presentation	2
14	Other Orienteering knowledge introduction	Pictures and text presentation	2

Hence, students should be guided to make good use of their spare time to learn Orienteering theories in the module of Orienteering theoretical APP in their mobile phones, with the help of PC version, online and off-line interactions in some mobile educational modules to further activate students' initiatives and enhance teachers' teaching efficacy.

The framework analysis of the theoretical study module of Orienteering APP

The choice of learning content and pedagogy

Mobile education has been widely used in each specific domain of education, from which we can tell that APP can facilitate the mobile education where students can both be receivers and discriminators of media. The information that is spread by mobile education should activate students' initiatives to be the transmitters. Only in this way is it possible to achieve the teaching objectives of theoretical study. Hence, Orienteering theoretical APP should contain decent teaching content (knowledge/news, short videos, etc.) and closely follow the publication strategy. The most pivotal teaching strategy is to simplify, fragment and systematize the Orienteering theories. Simplification is to divide and reorganize the theories into single and readily comprehensible knowledge point so as to strengthen the users' experience. Second, fragmentation is connect the segments whose relationship is rather loose, such as map symbols, with terrain and Live video which are easy for mobile publication. Finally, systematization is using the teaching strategies as guideline, respectively systematizing all the Orienteering theories and setting the content that is significant mobile one as APP module. Content that can not be mobile easily, such as game testing and knowledge jigsaw puzzle will be formed as guidance and put into PC version.

The deign ideas of module function

The theoretical module of Orienteering APP includes nearly 14 modules, which requires us to take further consideration on integrated factors. First and foremost, the module should be strongly implantable. Theoretical modules should be independent and time-efficient if it want to be added into the APP. Moreover, the teaching content of the module should have different levels. Based on the needed teaching objectives, the module should specify the learning content into small pieces. Yet importantly, there should be transition modules before and after the theoretical modules. Those transition modules

should at least contain autonomy learning module, Live-broadcasting platform module, interaction and sharing module and testing module. (see figure 2)

Number	Transition module	Introduction of the module content	Resource providers	Learning subjects
1	Autonomy learning module	Introduction; Fundamental knowledge of maps; Symbol recognition; physical training theories	Teachers	Students
2	Live-broadcasting platform module	Introduction of compass; Professional technical theories; Cartographic drawing; Competition appreciation; Short videos	Websites; Teachers	Students
3	Interaction and sharing module	Professional technical knowledge; Professional race skills; Principles and judgement; Field survival knowledge	Teachers; Students	Students
4	Testing game module	3D Game; Knowledge jigsaw puzzle	Corporate; Teachers; Students	Students

Furthermore, the module should provide the users with excellent playback function where the users can learn from their routes, learning progress and online sign-in. Interactive experience is also an essential function of theoretical module that learners can exchange their learning experiences and problems at their convenience with teachers or peers. Finally, the enjoyment of the module can attract more users and make the theoretical tests more direct and vivid by using 3D Game and knowledge jigsaw puzzle.

The introduction of parameter of APP design

The overall design of the APP

Demands on users' need

This programme divides Orienteering theoretical education into 14 basic theoretical modules and 4 transition modules, along with two ways of registration entry: Competitive users and recreational users.

1) Systematic function and performance

This characteristics of this APP are implantable, progressive, transitional, able to playback, interactive and interesting.

2) Statistics management and input and output demands

Users are divided as VIP member and register member, with the status updating by accumulated points system. In addition, the service side management is allowed to monitor the user number of recreational and competitive members so that the staff can provide better service.

The access to the statistics input and output system is divided by system administrators and register members. If the users would like to hold an interactive facetime or make a comment, they should be authorized by the system administrators.

3) Fault handling demands

When there is malfunction, people who are system administrators or authorized by them can have access to deal with the malfunction.

Operating environment

The systematic operating environment is Linux system. The domain name of the website should apply for the Chinese version. There should be icloud space so as to store video clips and documents. The

maximum limit of uploading is 50M.

Operating device

This APP should use the Mobile Terminal as hardware, including smart phones, tablet computers and computers. This APP is mainly focus on smart phone usage.

Fundamental design ideas and treatment scheme

The fundamental design ideas of this APP will be noted by categories in the entry of software deign registration and will simplify all the design hierarchy. The treatment scheme is using graphic form and listing them to the end-users.

The design of APP modules

The opening page of APP

The newest notification announcement of Orienteering and quick access to four basic modules.

Summary of each module content

- 1) Personal center: modification of personal information; collects; share; feedback; APP instruction, etc. The personal center will facilitate the personal learning process and information management.
- 2) Learning module: Users are encouraged to collect or update significant passages, pictures and video clips about Orienteering to enrich the module. They can readily search for their favor content by recognizing recreational and competitive modules.
- 3) Sharing module: A platform for Orienteering ideas, excitement and experience exchanging.
- 4) Live-broadcasting platform: Users have the chance to watch international Orienteering races and learn from them.
- 5) Testing game module: Through various games the users are able to practise some basic abilities of Orienteering.

The prospect of Orienteering theoretical APP

Mobile education is the pivotal innovation of traditional Orienteering learning methods in the mobile Internet era

The design of theoretical study modules is the outcome of combination of Internet technology and subject education. The novel technologies such as Artificial Intelligence and Big Data Analysis strengthen the immersive experience of Orienteering and bring opportunities to Orienteering theoretical study which requires practicality and context. There should be further exploration on the how to apply the newest Internet technology to Orienteering APP theoretical study module and how to introduce the most appropriate content to the users by observing their off-line courses, analyzing their dynamic needs and holding micro-teaching.

The further development of mobile education may trigger the formation of micro Orienteering communities and generalize closer relationships

The modules of Orienteering theoretical APP may become the model case of combining educational technology and Orienteering. We can utilize educational technology, with the help of customized module tutoring, to provide direct and responsible assistance for those learners who are keen on Orienteering theories and practice.

With the development of Live-broadcasting interaction and short videos sharing trend, Orienteering theoretical APP will be promoted to the convenient and intelligent orientation

The Orienteering theoretical APP can take advantage of interactive Live-broadcasting platform to diversify the teacher-student interactions, especially through the Live short videos and recorded icloud videos. Learners are exposed to recorded icloud videos to learn and share their knowledge and skills at any time in order to perceive a decent personal learning experience.

References

- Tang, X. G. (2016). Brief review of One-Hundred-Meter Orienteering Education. *Contemporary Sports Technology*, 6(35), 207-208+210.
- Ji, X. (2015). Investigating and analyzing the current situation of Orienteering education of Changchun Normal University. *Jilin University*.
- Ke, H. Y. (2012). The current situation and strategy of Orienteering : focusing on Guangzhou private schools Orienteering education. *Huazhong Normal University*.
- Chen, W. (2010). Exploration of introducing Orienteering to primary school sports and health classroom teaching. *Huadong Normal University*.
- Cheung, X. A., Hou, Z. R., & Wu, L. (2010). An experimental comparison between traditional education and Internet education of Orienteering. *The Journal of Zhaoqing College*, 31(02), 90-92.
- Cheng, L., & Zeng, L. P. (2010). A study of the situation of university Orienteering course selection. *Chinese Extramural Education*. (04), 154-155.
- Wang, X. M., & Cheung, X. (2009). Exploration of University Orienteering classroom teaching module design. *The Journal of Xinyang College (philosophy and social science version)*, 29(06), 93-96.
- Cheng, F., & Huang, M. (2009). A study on the application of multiple intelligence theory in Orienteering training. *The Journal of Jilin Sports College*, 25(01), 41-42.
- Huang, G. L. (2008) A study on Chinese Orienteering curricula construction. *Sports and Science Research*, (04), 102-104.
- Ding, H. Y. (2008). Investigating the Orienteering theory and its current situation of implementation in Jiangsu Province regular educational institutions. *Yangzhou University*.
- Yu, H. (2005). A study of training orienteers' awareness of principles. *Journal of Physical Education*, (05), 118-119.
- Wu, C. W. (2019). Evaluating the construction of Orienteering teaching content of University's social sports major. *The Journal of Heilong Jiang Science*, 10(19), 20-21.